

QUIZ**LAST NAME: CARTWRIGHT-JOHNSON****FIRST NAME: SHAWN****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: SIX (6)****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied U.S. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 13%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which is not an element of academic argument?

- Making a claim.
- Providing evidence.
- Explain reasoning.
- Intimidating an opponent.¹**

2. Which of these should not apply to the Literature Review Chapter?

- Identifying gaps in previous research.

1. Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 52–53.

- Removing contradictory literature from the discourse.²**
 - Placing the new research in the context of existing literature.
 - Identifying contradictions and limitations in the literature.
3. Which chapter of the research paper presents the rationale for the research, population, sample, and quality assurance?
- Introduction.
 - Findings.
 - Conclusion.
 - Methodology.³**
4. Which citation represents the correct formulation of the Turabian bibliography reference for a book with two authors?
- Choi, Suanne Y.P., and Yinni Peng, *Masculine Promise; Migration, Family, and Gender in China* (Oakland: University of California Press, 2016), 111-12.⁴**
 - Suanne Y.P. Choi and Yinni Peng, *Masculine Promise: Migration, Family and Gender in China* (Oakland: University of California Press, 2016), 111-12.
 - Choi S. and Peng Y., *Masculine Promise: Migration, Family and Gender in China* (Oakland: University of California Press, 2016), 111-12.

2. Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 79.

3. Adu, Philip. *Writing the Methodology Chapter of your Dissertation* (YouTube, 2016).

4. Turabian et al. *A Manual for Writers*, 151.

- Suanne Y.P. Choi and Yinni Peng, *Masculine Promise: Migration, Family and Gender in China* (Oakland: University of California Press, 2016), 111-12.
5. A researcher does not have to cite his sources of information or give credit where...
- It is the researcher's previously published work.
- The researcher is not using the words of his source verbatim.
- Information is common knowledge.**⁵
- The source is more than thirty years old.
6. Which quotation represents proper U.S. English format for punctuation and quotations?
- 'The Minister shouted, "This meeting is over!" and left the room.'
- "The Minister shouted, 'This meeting is over!' and left the room."**⁶
- "The Minister shouted, "This meeting is over!" and left the room".
- 'The Minister shouted, 'This meeting is over!' and left the room.'
7. Using a software program such as Zotero can aid the research and writing process, but Zotero is not used for which of the following
- Creating a bibliography.
- Sharing your research with sources.
- Selecting topic.**⁷

5. Laurent Cleenerwerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2024), 37.

6. [Ibid., 37](#).

7. Laurent Cleenerwerck, *Zotero Training 01*, (Vimeo 2016).

Deleted: Cleenerwerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2024), 37.

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Managing references.

8. Which of these statements is not true about the abstract of a research paper

The abstract should state what you did during the research.⁸

The abstract should state what you discovered during the research.

The abstract helps the reader determine the paper's relevance to the reader's research.

The abstract appears on its page and is usually 200-300 words long.

9. In academic writing, the style guide is essential; which is not influenced by the style guide?

Uniformity of references.

Content relating to the subject matter of the paper.⁹

Consistency in spelling, abbreviation, and punctuation.

Font size, style, and usage.

10. The reliability of a source may be in question where...

The book or article is peer-reviewed.

A reputable press published the source.

The source has been cited frequently by other reputable scholars.

Commented [DG1]: This book was not cited in full in the first instance!

8. Bloomberg and Volpe 2019, 68; Sampson 2017, 26.

9. European Commission, 4; Turabian et al., 293-420.

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The source does not have notes or a bibliography.¹⁰

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Adu, Philip. *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study*. YouTube. 2016.
- Bloomberg, Linda, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. 4th ed. Los Angeles: Sage, 2019.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent, dir. *Zotero Training 01*. Vimeo. 2016.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *How to Write a Response Paper*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2024
- European Union. 2016. "English Style Guide." Accessed July 22, 2024. https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/styleguide_english_dgt_en.pdf.
- Sampson, James. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. 2nd ed. Tallahassee, FL: Florida State University Libraries, 2017.
- Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. 9th ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Commented [DG2]: The referencing of EU's book is incorrect. Reference it as a hardcover book. You can use the following link as a quick guide but be very STRICT with the format and punctuation - <https://library.austincc.edu/help/turabian/>

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰. Turabian et al. 33-34.